

THE ABYSS

(Explanatory Notes)

INTRODUCTION

THE ABYSS is a graphic novel that deals with the issues of women, memory, and space. While the abyss forms the creative backdrop, this novel marks the release of imaginative energy, stories, and incidents, as well as bouts of frustration in the lives of three college students, who discuss and state the relevance of Kari and Persepolis in today's world.

What does the TITLE mean?

1. The title is open to interpretations.
2. Abyss literally means “a profound, bottomless, or unfathomably deep space where things unknown and undiscovered exist.” We are using the abyss for the bombardment of our creative energy.
3. The Abyss holds deep meaning from the theological and scientific as well as psychological point of view.
4. The colour majorly associated with the Abyss is blue (sometimes, black), and therefore, the font colour is also blue.

COVER PAGE: *(completely open to interpretations!)*

1. The cover page is the only coloured page to help the readers visualise the dominant colours throughout the novel.
2. **Yellow colour** indicates happiness, courage, optimism, and creativity, but lurking in the background, the dark side of yellow is cowardice, betrayal, and madness. The golden yellow colour also represents the Golden Womb in Hindu mythology, which is the source of the creation of the universe.
3. **Brown colour** is to remind us of our raw connections with the natural world and help us in settling entangled feelings. *(This graphic novel is also a raw production by three amateurs, by the way.)*
4. **Green colour** is associated with our desire to foster understanding and self-acceptance.

Card Symbolism - To make representation easier in further pages of the novel, we decided to use the playing cards as stand-in symbols for our own selves. Indication is that we are putting our cards on the table, which means we are being completely open and honest about our intentions and ideas in the entire novel. While diamonds, spades, and clubs represent the material world (merchant, military, agriculture), hearts represent the spiritual world (church, religion). The Heart throughout the novel is like an absent figure—not there but much needed. The heart symbol is for the readers to interpret as they deem fit. It can be the readers themselves.

REASON BEHIND THE GIRLS STANDING WITH FACES IN THREE DIFFERENT DIRECTIONS

1. We tried to recreate the figure of Brahma in Hindu mythology—the creator of the universe. In a figurative way, the heads in different directions represent the intellect, ego, and self-confidence.
2. Lightly referring to the mythology of Brahma and Shatarupa, it is to understand how we are trying to deconstruct the myth of the creation of the First Woman, Shatarupa, as per Hindu mythology. In a world ordered by sexual imbalance, pleasure in looking has been split between active/male and passive/female. The deliberately closed eyes of the three girls, contrary to the open “active” eyes of Brahma, fixed and staring at the beauty of Shatarupa, aim to deconstruct the notion of the determining male gaze that projects its fantasy onto the female figure, who is forced to tile accordingly.
3. We have considered the pros and cons of this representation. **It is not intended to offend anyone.**
4. The girl standing in a position similar to Brahma—creator of the universe—is to explain that we, as women, are trying to create a space, a microcosm, or a universe for our own selves.

PAGE 1: PROLOGUE

1. Yet again, feel free to imagine what it is trying to do!
2. The aim is to show the creation of a universe or a space.
3. It can be interpreted as **an outer space, or a creative space, or a microcosm, or maybe a space somewhere within us where memories exist.**
4. All three girls are breaking into the space through their individual rockets (Sapna represented by Diamond, Niharika by Club, and Bhavika by Spade). Also, we have

bubbles on our heads so that we can breathe in the space we are travelling into.

5. The discussion is online, via a remote medium, and the channel of communication is the air. Thus, it can also signify the wireless space in between the online worlds.

PART 1 - CHILDHOOD (Page 2)

From the above universe, we have chosen a particular molecule or creative space to explore.

1. At the centre, it is us with all sorts of expressions on our faces. *Interpret them with your own set of meanings!*
2. The panels are in a film/photographic reel form. After all, memories are just stories without evidence.
3. **The panels move in a anticlockwise direction**—to challenge the clockwise dominant narrative. Also, we are not in a “normally” perceived world, so everything is open to explorations here!

(Page 3)

1. The panels are in a film/photographic reel form.
2. *The way memory works can be painful or restorative but is always a dynamic process of seeking and re-making. It both unifies and fragments experience. It locates us as agents within our own lives, which inevitably we see as a story. Memories of the past are memories not of facts but of our imagining of the facts. So, we need to be cautious about our memories and how we develop them in a red room but also embrace the creative aspect they can bring to our writing.*
3. The negative vibes in the last reel are oozing out. No one is truly free from the horror or the trauma of the past. Memories always bring back discomfoting feelings.

(Page 4)

1. The long hair represents societal norms, and the scissors represent the courage Bhavika had to cut her hair or free herself from the norms in her own possible way. The cut hair represents a new beginning.
2. Reference to Kari and Persepolis.

PART 2 – SOCIETY (Page 5)

1. We have tried to present the hypocrisy of the people as we have experienced in our own lives.

PART 3 – SEXUALITY, RELATIONSHIPS AND MENTAL HEALTH

(Page 6): *Go! Give it a read!*

(Page 7)

1. The heart is shackled, and if we try to free the heart, it will bleed. There is no key to freeing oneself from social constraints.
2. It is a depiction of the inner world of a person (here, maybe Niharika's world), a graveyard with all the cells of feelings that died an unfair death under the stranglehold of society.
3. Two persons hugging each other—a symbol of sexual revolution
4. “THE SCREAM” by Edvard Munch (1893) is there to symbolise the inner conflict and disorder in the world of a person who fails to completely formulate the dialogue bubble and explain what she/he is feeling.

(Page 8): Open to interpretation! It also acts as a relief page—a simple but profound page.

(Page 9)

1. Sapna is in a meditating pose, but the satire lies in the fact that during meditation, we think of nothing and better concentration, but here, she is thinking of dating and all. Not to mention, the packet of chips and coffee in her hand.

(Page 10): *Go! Give it a read!*

(Page 11)

Bhavika is in a foetus-like position, which represents the inner child, or like a baby who speaks in her own language, which adults cannot understand.

A foetus is a living soul that is in a safe womb where castes, religion, gender ... nothing can come. It can live without any social constraints and beliefs until it is brought out into the world.

Notice that Bhavika hardly spoke a word since the last page—when memories of the past come and take over you, it is difficult to fight them and resurface to the real world. Companionship and understanding act like a ray of hope and reason to let go of the past. Friends and family teach you how to live again.

(Page 12)

1. This page is an abstract representation of the real world as well as the inner world.
OPEN TO INTERPRETATIONS!
2. This page explains the various reasons one has to go to the terrace or the rooftop.
3. Bhavika went to the rooftop to become the Breeze. It metaphorically means to commit suicide or disappear into thin air. However, while on the rooftop, the breeze (a dotted, airy figure) by blowing through her hand, in a way to hold it, pulls her back as if saying that life will give you many second chances but death will never.
4. Bhavika realised that she too, like the breeze, must become a person who will learn to understand others, push them forward in a way of motivation, or pull them backwards when things become dangerous in a way to help them. She must become an observer, just like the breeze that passes through all nooks and corners of places, times, and things; a person who cannot bring big changes in the lives of others but simply, at times, taps them on the shoulders, pats their backs, or brushes through their hair (just like the breeze), appreciating their efforts and thanking them for being alive.

(Page 13)

1. The discussion is nearing the end. This page marks the end of our journey to space (creative, outer, inner, micro-cosmos, etc.) and return to the real world.
2. Niharika and Sapna realise what becoming the breeze meant. And there's profound silence.
3. To keep the conversation going, Bhavika asks them to crack a joke, but Niharika says, "How can we..." to indicate that becoming the Breeze is no matter to joke about.
4. There is silence and shorter sentences.
5. The representation of the breeze continues. There is a telephone connecting with the Breeze as if we are calling her.
6. The representation is such that all the cards are freely falling along the flow of the wind.
7. Indication—"All" the cards we played and showed in the novel eventually go back into the same deck they came from."

LAST PAGE: PERSONIFICATION

1. The breeze is personified to indicate a form of epiphany, serendipity, or serenity. A meditative form with eyes closed in contrast with the deliberate shutting of the eyes on the cover page.
 2. She is also the carrier of all spaces and memories of times, places, and histories. Breeze, which is an observer of everyone's lives and carries all the secrets, is unexplored yet.
 3. The rockets are going back from space into reality.
 4. The laptop disconnects. The meeting is over.
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